

AN X-RAY INVESTIGATION OF THE CRYSTALS OF *p*-AMINO BENZOIC ACID. THE SPACE GROUP.

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Crystals of *p*-aminobenzoic acid [$C_6H_4(NH_2)(COOH)$] belong to the monoclinic prismatic class. It is difficult to obtain them in a well developed form. For the purpose of the present investigation the crystals were prepared by the slow evaporation of the solution of the substance in rectified spirit. The crystals which were obtained by repeated crystallisations were in the form of rhombic plates. The shorter diagonal of the plates was found to be the *b*-axis by means of Laue photograph, taken with the flat face normal to the beam. Only three faces, viz., (100), (101) and (10 $\bar{1}$) which contain the *b*-axis are mentioned by Groth ("Chemische crystallographie," IV, p. 509). By taking several rotation photographs, it was found that the flat face is (101). The crystal was then suitably adjusted and the rotation photographs were taken about *a*, *b* and *c* axes (Plates I, II and III) and about 101 and 10 $\bar{1}$ axes. The last two photographs were taken for the sake of confirmation. The following were the lengths obtained.

$$a=12.26 \text{ \AA} ; b=8.61 \text{ \AA} ; c=6.30 \text{ \AA}.$$

These lengths give the following axial ratio :—

$$a : b : c = 1.424 : 1 : 0.7316.$$

This ratio agrees with that given in Groth (*loc. cit.*)

$$a : b : c = 1.4403 : 1 : 0.7312.$$

Further the measurements from the photographs taken about 101 and 10 $\bar{1}$ axes give the same value of the angle β ($100^\circ 10'$ as mentioned in Groth).

Oscillation photographs were taken about three crystallographic axes at intervals of 15° and the indices of the planes corresponding to the spots on the oscillation photographs were worked out by means of Bernal's chart. The intensities of the planes were determined by eye-estimation and the usual symbols have been used. The list of the planes observed is given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Axial planes	Prism planes.	Prism planes.	Prism planes.
	(hol)	(okl)	(hko)
002 s	101 v. s.	011 v. s.	110 m.
020 m. s.	103 m. s.	012 m. s.	120 v. s.
040 m.	101 v. s.	013 s.	130 m. s.
200 v. s.	103 m. s.	021 m. s.	140 w.
400 m. s.	202 m. s.	022 m. s.	210 v. s.
600 w.	301 m. s.	023 w.	220 v. s.
	402 s.	031 v. w.	230 w.
	402 v. w.	032 m. s.	240 w.
	501 w. m.	041 v. w.	310 m. s.
	501 w. m.		320 m. s.
	602 s.		330 m.
			340 w.
			430 w. m.
			510 w. m.
			520 w.
			610 m.
			620 w.

Rotation Photograph.

Plate I.

a-rotation

Plate II.

b-rotation

Plate III.

c-rotation

TABLE II.

General planes,

$1\bar{1}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$2\bar{1}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$3\bar{1}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$4\bar{1}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$5\bar{1}\bar{1}$ m.	$6\bar{1}\bar{1}$ w.
$1\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$2\bar{1}\bar{2}$ s.	$3\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m. s.	$4\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.	$5\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$6\bar{1}\bar{1}$ w.
$1\bar{1}\bar{3}$ s.	$2\bar{1}\bar{3}$ w.	$3\bar{1}\bar{3}$ v.w.	$4\bar{1}\bar{3}$ m.	$5\bar{1}\bar{1}$ m.	$6\bar{2}\bar{1}$ w.
$1\bar{1}\bar{1}$ s.	$2\bar{1}\bar{1}$ m.s.	$3\bar{1}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$4\bar{1}\bar{1}$ s.	$5\bar{1}\bar{2}$ w.m.	$6\bar{2}\bar{1}$ v.w.
$1\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.	$2\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$3\bar{1}\bar{2}$ w.m.	$4\bar{1}\bar{2}$ m.	$5\bar{2}\bar{1}$ m.	
$1\bar{1}\bar{3}$ m.s.	$2\bar{1}\bar{3}$ w.	$3\bar{2}\bar{2}$ v.w.	$4\bar{2}\bar{1}$ s.	$5\bar{2}\bar{2}$ w.	
$1\bar{2}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$2\bar{2}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$3\bar{2}\bar{2}$ w.	$4\bar{2}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$5\bar{2}\bar{1}$ m.	
$1\bar{2}\bar{2}$ m.	$2\bar{2}\bar{2}$ m.	$3\bar{3}\bar{1}$ s.	$4\bar{2}\bar{3}$ v.w.	$5\bar{2}\bar{2}$ w.m.	
$1\bar{2}\bar{3}$ w.m.	$2\bar{2}\bar{1}$ s.	$3\bar{3}\bar{2}$ m.	$4\bar{2}\bar{1}$ m.	$5\bar{3}\bar{1}$ w.m.	
$1\bar{2}\bar{1}$ m.s.	$2\bar{2}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$3\bar{3}\bar{1}$ w.	$4\bar{2}\bar{2}$ s.		
$1\bar{2}\bar{2}$ w.	$2\bar{3}\bar{1}$ m.s.	$3\bar{3}\bar{2}$ w.	$4\bar{3}\bar{1}$ m.		
$1\bar{2}\bar{3}$ w.	$2\bar{3}\bar{2}$ m.	$3\bar{4}\bar{1}$ w.m.	$4\bar{3}\bar{1}$ m.		
$1\bar{3}\bar{1}$ v.s.	$2\bar{3}\bar{1}$ m.	$3\bar{4}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$4\bar{4}\bar{1}$ s.		
$1\bar{3}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$2\bar{3}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$3\bar{4}\bar{1}$ v.w.	$4\bar{4}\bar{1}$ m.s.		
$1\bar{3}\bar{1}$ m.	$2\bar{4}\bar{1}$ s.	$3\bar{4}\bar{2}$ m.			
$1\bar{3}\bar{2}$ m.s.	$2\bar{4}\bar{2}$ w.				
$1\bar{4}\bar{1}$ v.w.	$2\bar{4}\bar{1}$ m.				

From the above list of planes it will be seen that (h0l) planes are halved if (h+1) is odd and (ok0) halved if k is odd. These halvings correspond to the space group C_{2h}^2 . The number of molecules in the unit cell required by the space group is four. The number of molecules calculated from the dimensions of the unit cell, and the density of crystals, 1.393 (Groth), is found to be four (actually 4.01). Hence, it appears that the molecules in the unit cell are asymmetric.

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